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EQA FOR POCT – OPPORTUNITIES FOR QUALITY, CHALLENGES FOR IMPLEMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

The use of point-of-care testing (POCT) is increasing in settings where the staff is not necessarily familiar with procedures that are routine for laboratory professionals. This raises the questions of responsibility for training, instructions for use, quality control, etc.

The POCT results are intended for immediate use and they have a direct effect on patient care. To ensure that the test is performed correctly and gives reliable results, internal quality control (IQC) and external quality assessment (EQA) should be a part of the POCT routine. Detailed instructions for sampling processing and analysis are of great importance for POCT units. EQA providers should offer clinically relevant programs and cover the total testing process including pre- and post-analytics in addition to the analytical phase. There is no exception when it comes to EQA for POCT. EQA samples should cover both abnormal and normal concentrations, they should be stable, homogenous, safe to use, commutable, as well as preferably ready-to-use for analysis in the same way as patient samples would be analyzed. In practice, EQA samples often need some pretreatment such as resuspension or reconstitution and this can cause challenges for POCT sites where no laboratory equipment is available. Instructions should be very straightforward and laboratory jargon should be avoided since this might be misinterpreted.

Participation in EQA programs can be voluntary or mandatory depending on national legislation, and both have pros and cons. When mandatory, this might be the only motivation for a testing site to participate and if the

success is not good enough, it might lead to restrictions in performing testing. When voluntary, some sites may choose not to participate if they do not see the importance and benefits of EQA and the costs might be considered too high. The motivation to participate should be an interest to increase the quality of the performance and accuracy of patient results. If the success is not within the accepted limits, it is of high importance to find and eliminate the root cause of the incorrect result. This should be seen as an educational situation and a possibility for improvement without the fear of reprimands, however, it is not a situation that can be overseen regardless of mandatory or voluntary EQA participation. When a result is acceptable, it indicates that the analysis was performed correctly and that the test/device is reliable.

When reporting EQA results to the participants, POCT sites have special needs. A report that is appropriate for laboratory professionals with detailed statistical analysis of the results might be too complicated for POCT users not familiar with expressions used in the laboratory. If the report is not understandable and beneficial for the user, this will decrease the motivation to participate in the EQA program. Each user should receive a report with the information they need for improving their processes and confirming the quality of their patient results.

In this talk, EQA for POCT with its opportunities for quality and challenges for implementation will be discussed with the help of examples from EQA schemes with POCT participants.

Key words: POCT; EQA; quality